

Conference Abstract

First insight into the composition and structure of macrozoobenthos in the area of the 'underwater petrified forest', Sozopol Bay (Black Sea)

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Abstract

The “Underwater Petrified Forest” in Sozopol Bay (Fig. 1) is one of the most remarkable marine habitats along the Bulgarian coast. This paleobotanical phenomenon consists of numerous well-preserved swamp cypress trunks and stumps dating back over 20 million years to the Miocene epoch. It is a globally rare underwater site of scientific importance, with only one other similar site documented so far, in the Gulf of Mexico. Despite its geological importance and distinctive physical characteristics, the biological communities associated with this habitat have until now remained poorly studied.

The present study provides the first data on the taxonomic composition and quantitative structure of macrobenthic communities inhabiting the fossilized wood formations as a substrate and microhabitat. During field campaigns in 2023 and 2024, SCUBA divers collected and processed qualitative and quantitative benthic samples following the best scientific diving practices and standards.

The analysis revealed a rich and functionally diverse macrobenthic fauna, including Porifera, Polychaeta, Bivalvia, Gastropoda, Decapoda, Bryozoa and Chordata. The highest abundances were recorded for polychaete worms (subclass Sedentaria),

surrounding sandy seabed was markedly poorer in sessile and hemisessile taxa, highlighting the role of the petrified structures as localized biodiversity hotspots. Beyond the macrobenthic assemblages, field observations also indicated higher fish abundance and species richness around the fossilised structures. These findings further highlight the broader ecological influence of this habitat

These initial results emphasise the ecological significance of the underwater petrified forest as a distinctive habitat that contributes to the local and regional biodiversity of benthic communities (Fig. 4). Given the anthropogenic pressure on the coastal ecosystems of the Black Sea, the site represents an invaluable natural archive and a baseline for future monitoring, conservation planning, and multidisciplinary research integrating ecology, geology, and paleobotany.

Keywords

underwater petrified forest, macrozoobenthos, biodiversity hotspots, Black sea

Presenting author

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**FIRST INSIGHT INTO THE COMPOSITION AND STRUCTURE OF MACROZOOBENTHOS
IN THE AREA OF THE 'UNDERWATER PETRIFIED FOREST', SOZOPOL BAY (BLACK SEA)**

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Introduction

The 'Underwater Petrified Forest' in Sozopol Bay is one of the most remarkable marine habitats along the Bulgarian coast. This paleobotanical site comprises numerous preserved swamp cypress trunks and stumps dating back over 20 million years to the Miocene epoch. It is a globally unique underwater site of scientific importance, with only one other similar site documented so far, in the Gulf of Mexico. Nevertheless, the associated biological diversity has remained poorly studied. This study presents the first data on the taxonomic composition and quantitative structure of macrobenthic communities inhabiting the petrified tree trunks as a substrate and microhabitat. During field campaigns in 2023 and 2024, SCUBA divers collected and processed qualitative and quantitative benthic samples following the best scientific diving practices and standard.

Results

Analysis revealed diverse macrobenthic groups, including Porifera, Polychaeta, Bivalvia, Gastropoda, Decapoda, Bryozoa and Chordata – totaly 11 taxonomic groups. The highest abundances were recorded for Polychaeta worms (subclass Sedentaria), mussels (primarily *Mytilus galloprovincialis* Lamarck, 1819) and crustaceans; other taxa also contributed to the overall structural diversity (Fig. 2). The abundance (calculated per 1 m² area) is highest in the Bivalvia (*M. galloprovincialis* - 5747 ind.), Polychaeta (*Spirorbis pusilla* Rathke, 1837 – 4358 ind.) as well as in *Amphibalanus* sp. (1024 ind.).

Fig. 2 – Average count of organisms per 1 m² in each hydrobiological group from the 14 quantitative samples.

Fig. 3 – Total count of organisms per 1 m² in every sample from the 14 quantitative samples.

Photo 2 – Collecting samples using SCUBA diving techniques; Photo: Ladislav Tsvetkov, BTV

Photo 3 – Collecting samples using SCUBA diving techniques; Photo: Ladislav Tsvetkov, BTV

Materials and Methods

The macrozooobenthos samples were collected using SCUBA diving techniques, following the guidelines of the Bulgarian National Association for Underwater Activities (bnaua.org) for scientific diving. In 2023-2024, depths of 18-22 metres were visited in the area of the Underwater Petrified Forest in Sozopol Bay. The material was manually collected from petrified wood structures and adjacent sediment surfaces overgrown with sessile benthos. A total of 14 quantitative samples (one to two frames measuring 11.5 x 12.5 cm) and six qualitative samples were collected. The samples were fixed in 4% formalin and subsequently processed using standard hydrobiological methods.

Fig. 1 – Location of the sampling points. Left: Sozopol bay, right: underwater SCUBA lines and petrified tree locations.

Fig. 4 – Location of the Underwater Petrified Forest in the Black Sea near Sozopol, Bulgaria (image generated by Map data© 2025, Geobase/GE/GRK).

Photo 1 – *Mytilus galloprovincialis* with attached Bryozoa colony, *Amphibalanus* sp., *Spirorbis pusilla* and *Sedentaria caetera*; Photo: L. Spasov

Photo 4 – *Corambe obscura* (A.E. Verrill, 1870) determined by Prof. P. Mihov from the sample collected from "The Snout" on 12.09.2024; Photo: L. Spasov

Photo 5 – *Leptochirona cinerea* (Simonsen, 1923) determined by Prof. P. Mihov from the sample collected from "The Hollow" on 12.09.2024; Photo: L. Spasov

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Discussion

The petrified wood was shown to provide a unique hard substrate supporting both sessile and mobile invertebrates, thereby enhancing local biodiversity compared to the surrounding sandy bottoms, which generally have a low richness of sessile and hemisessile organisms. The Underwater Petrified Forest in Sozopol Bay is an important local biodiversity hotspot. In the face of increasing global anthropogenic impact, it provides a baseline for future monitoring and conservation, and it should be preserved as both heritage and a vital element of the Black Sea ecosystem.

Figure 4. [doi](#)

The presented poster.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.